
A THREE POINT DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

Picture: Yan Wong (Pixabay)

BASED ON
THE GENERAL FINNISH DMP GUIDANCE

by Tuuli working group

2021

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GENERAL FINNISH DMP GUIDANCE

0. PROJECT DETAILS

Include background information such as the name of the applicant and the project, the project number, the funding programme and the version of the DMP.

A Three Point DMP Performance Criteria

Based on the General Finnish DMP Guidance

A Data Management Plan created using DMPTuuli

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Template: No external funding

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Grant number: -

Project abstract:

A three point performance criteria is modified from the Finnish DMP evaluation guide (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4729832>) prepared in the Spring of 2021 by Tuuli working group: Sirpa Aalto, Minna Ahokas, Jari Friman, Siiri Fuchs, Tuija Korhonen, Mari Elisa Kuusniemi, Kati Laakso, Mietta Lennes, Soile Manninen, Mikko Ojanen, Jukka Rantasaari (chair), Mika E. Virtanen, Qingbo Xu. The guide is loosely based on Data Management Plan Evaluation Rubric by Science Europe published in *Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition (2021)* (https://scienceeurope.org/media/4brkxe5/se_rdm_practical_guide_extended_final.pdf).

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Layout: Jukka Rantasaari

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

Project details coversheet is included in the plan containing information of the

- ❖ Project title
- ❖ Funder (if applicable)
- ❖ Grant number (if applicable)
- ❖ Funding instrument (if applicable) (e.g. Lippulaiva)
- ❖ Principal investigator
- ❖ Institution
- ❖ Other contributors
- ❖ ORCID -researcher IDs of all contributors
- ❖ Date of updates
- ❖ Abstract of the project

SATISFACTORY:

Describes the

- ❖ Title
- ❖ Principal investigator
- ❖ Date of the latest update
- ❖ Abstract of the project.

POOR:

No background information of the project is given.

1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF DATA

1.1 Data Description

Briefly describe what types of data you are collecting or producing. In addition, explain what kinds of already existing data you will (re)use. List, for example, the types of texts, images, photographs, measurements, statistics, physical samples or codes.

Categorise your data in a table or with a clear list, for example:

- A) previously collected existing data which is being reused in this project,
- B) data collected for this project,
- C) data produced as an outcome of the research process.

The categorisation can form a general structure for the rest of the DMP.

List the file formats for each data set. In some cases, the file formats used during the research project may differ from those used in archiving the data after the project. List both. The file format is a primary factor in the accessibility and reusability of your data in the future.

In the DMP, what is important is to describe the required disk space, not how many informants participated in the project. A rough estimation of the size of the data is sufficient, for example, less than 100 GB, approx. 1 TB or several petabytes.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Use a table or bullet points for a concise way to present data types, file formats, the software used and the size of the data. Examples of file formats are .csv, .txt, .docx, .xlsx and .tif.
- ❖ Make sure to describe any special or uncommon software necessary to view or use the data, especially if the software is coded in your project.
- ❖ You can also estimate the increase in data production or collection during the project for a specific time period: "The project is producing/collecting approximately 100 GB of data per week."
- ❖ **AVOID OVERLAPS WITH THE RESEARCH PLAN!** Data analysis and methodological issues related to data and materials should be described in your research plan.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly lists data sets/types in a categorized table. The list is in line with the research plan and the rest of the DMP.
- ❖ Categorization acknowledges different data handling needs (for example sensitive/confidential data):
 - A) existing data which is being reused with licences or user rights described briefly. (More detailed description is found in section 2.2.)
 - B) new data produced/collected,
 - C) data produced (derivates) as an outcome of data analysis of this project.
- ❖ Explains why certain formats have been chosen and indicates if they are in open and standard format. If a proprietary format is used, it explains why.
- ❖ Explains if any special or uncommon software are needed to view or use the data.
- ❖ Clearly describes how data volume or its accumulation has been calculated.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Describes or lists what data types will be used or generated and their associated data formats.
- ❖ List of datatypes is in line with the research plan and the rest of the DMP (no data set is missing compared to research methods or other data sources).
- ❖ Provides information about the estimated data volume or how the data volume accumulates.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides no or little details on what data types will be generated without a valid reason for this omission.
- ❖ Only lists/describes the kinds of data without specifying their formats.
- ❖ Only lists formats, without specifying the kinds of data.
- ❖ Does not provide an estimate of data volume.
- ❖ Claims that there is no data produced or used.

1.2 Data Quality

Explain how the data collection, analysis and processing methods used may affect the quality of the data and how you will minimise the risks related to data accuracy.

Data quality control ensures that no data is accidentally changed and that the accuracy of the data is maintained over its entire life cycle. Quality problems can emerge due to the technical handling, converting or transferring of data, or during its contextual processing and analysis.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Transcriptions of audio or video interviews should be checked by someone other than the transcriber.
- ❖ Analog material should be digitised in the highest resolution possible for accuracy.
- ❖ In all conversions, maintaining the original information content should be ensured.
- ❖ Software-producing checksums should be used.
- ❖ Organise training sessions and set guidelines to ensure that everyone in your research group can implement quality control and anticipate the risks related to the quality of the data.
- ❖ **AVOID OVERLAPS WITH THE RESEARCH PLAN!** Issues related to data analysis, methods and tools should be described in your research plan, that is, do not include, for example, instrument calibration descriptions here.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly recognizes possible error sources to ensure the quality of data during the data lifecycle.
- ❖ Describes appropriate practices (data capture, validation/monitoring, versioning, logs, etc) chosen for each tasks of the data handling to ensure high quality of data.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Describes the approach taken to ensure and document data quality control during its lifecycle.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides no information or only a vague mention on how data quality is controlled and documented during the lifetime of the project.
- ❖ Confuses research quality and data quality. No explanation or examples of data quality control are given in the data management context.

2. ETHICAL AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

2.1 Legal and Ethical Issues

All types of research data involve questions of rights and legal and ethical issues. Demonstrate that you are aware of the relevant legislation related to your data processing. If you are handling personal or sensitive information, describe how you will ensure privacy protection and data anonymisation or pseudonymisation.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Check your institutional ethical guidelines, data privacy guidelines and data security policy, and prepare to follow the instructions that are given in these guidelines.
- ❖ If your research is to be reviewed by an ethical committee, outline in your DMP how you will comply with the protocol (e.g., how you will remove personal or sensitive information from your data before sharing data to ensure privacy protection).
- ❖ Will you process personal data? If you intend to do so, please detail what type of personal data you will collect.
- ❖ All data related to an identified or identifiable person is personal data. Information such as names, telephone numbers, location data and information on the congenital diseases of the individual's grandparents is personal data.
- ❖ Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman (<https://tietosuoja.fi/en/processing-of-personal-data>)
- ❖ AVOID OVERLAPS WITH THE RESEARCH PLAN! Details of the ethical issues, the ethical committee statements and the use of laboratory animals should be described in the research plan.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly indicates whether personal data, sensitive data, copyrighted material and/or any other legally restricted data will be processed (collected and/or used) as part of the project.
- ❖ Identifies the legal requirements and ethical practices that apply to processing the data.
- ❖ If applicable, explains how compliance with applicable legislation will be ensured, for example by some of the following means:
 - ❖ identifying the Data Controller and a potential legal basis for processing personal data according to GDPR (e.g., research in the public interest, or informed consent),
 - ❖ considering the need for anonymization, pseudonymization, encryption or other appropriate safeguards when appropriate,
- ❖ If applicable, provides details of ethical issues that may affect data storage, transfer, use, sharing and/ or preservation, and demonstrates that adequate measures are in place to manage ethical requirements.
- ❖ If applicable, mentions whether ethical review is being pursued. In case ethical approval has already been obtained, refers to the relevant committee and documents.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Clearly indicates whether personal data, sensitive data, copyrighted material and/or any other legally restricted data will be processed (collected and/or used) as part of the project.
- ❖ Identifies the legal requirements and ethical practices that apply to processing the data.
- ❖ If applicable, identifies the Data Controller or describes how this issue will be settled.

POOR:

- ❖ Does not clearly indicate whether personal data, sensitive data and/or any other legally restricted data will be used as part of the project.
- ❖ Does not provide sufficient explanation why ethical issues are not relevant for the research project.

2.2 Managing Intellectual Property Rights (page 1)

Describe how you will agree upon the rights of use related to your research data – including the collected, produced and (re)used data of your project. Here, you can employ your categorisation in the first question. Each of these categories involves different rights and licenses. Describe the transfer of rights procedures relevant to your project. Describe confidentiality issues if applicable in your project.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Check your organisational data policy for ownership, the right of use and the right to distribute.
- ❖ Have you gained consent for data preservation and sharing?
- ❖ Agreements on ownership and rights of use should be made as early as possible in the project life cycle.
- ❖ Consider the funder's policy.
- ❖ It is recommended to make all of the research data, code and software created within a research project available for reuse, e.g., under a Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/choose/>), GNU (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>) or MIT license (<https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>), or under another relevant license.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

Data rights and agreements

- ❖ Identifies the owner or rights holder of the data and the rationale concerning data ownership.
- ❖ Identifies the licenses or other terms and conditions that will apply to data re-use or describes how this issue will be settled.
- ❖ If applicable, explains how intellectual property rights will be managed and what agreements are required, e.g., for transfer of rights.
- ❖ In the case of multi-partner projects and multiple data owners, explains how their roles and responsibilities regarding the data are addressed in the consortium agreement.

Data protection

- ❖ If none of the restrictions mentioned below are applicable, this is stated clearly.
- ❖ Explains how the lawful processing of personal data will be ensured both during the project and regarding potential re-use of the data (e.g., compatibility with the legal purpose of research in the public interest, or informed consent).
- ❖ Mentions how the project complies with the funder's data sharing policy and if it does not, explains why this is not possible.

2.2 Managing Intellectual Property Rights (page 2)

Describe how you will agree upon the rights of use related to your research data – including the collected, produced and (re)used data of your project. Here, you can employ your categorisation in the first question. Each of these categories involves different rights and licenses. Describe the transfer of rights procedures relevant to your project. Describe confidentiality issues if applicable in your project.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Check your organisational data policy for ownership, the right of use and the right to distribute.
- ❖ Have you gained consent for data preservation and sharing?
- ❖ Agreements on ownership and rights of use should be made as early as possible in the project life cycle.
- ❖ Consider the funder's policy.
- ❖ It is recommended to make all of the research data, code and software created within a research project available for reuse, e.g., under a Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/choose/>), GNU (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>) or MIT license (<https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>), or under another relevant license.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Identifies the owner or rights holder of the data (or mentions how this issue will be addressed at an early stage).
- ❖ Describes, at least on a general level, how the legal and ethical issues, stated in 2.1, will be taken into account when processing and sharing the data; or provides an explanation of why no special measures are required.
- ❖ On a general level, describes the agreements concerning the rights to use the data, but possibly without specifying them according to different types of data (as listed in section 1.1).
- ❖ On a general level, describes the terms and conditions that will apply to the processing and re-use of the data.

POOR:

- ❖ Does not identify the owner or rights holders of the data.
- ❖ Does not discuss the effects that legal issues can have on the processing and sharing of the data (or a subset of it), and does not provide a good explanation for not doing so.
- ❖ In case of a multi-partner project, does not address the legal and ethical roles and responsibilities of the project participants and does not provide a good explanation for not doing so.

3. DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

3.1 Metadata & Documentation

Data documentation enables data sets and files to be discovered, used and properly cited by other users (human or computer). Documentation includes essential information regarding the data, for example, where, when, why and how the data were collected, processed and interpreted. Without the proper documentation, your data is useless. Describe the tool, such as Qvain, that you will use to describe your data sets. Do not mention metadata standards if you do not use them. You can anticipate the open accessibility of your data and its description already here. However, a detailed description of which part of your data can be set openly available will be included in Section 5 below.

AVOID OVERLAPS WITH THE RESEARCH PLAN! The data-level documentation (<https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/document/data-level.aspx>) and details about experiments, analytical methods and the research context belong to the research plan. In the DMP you should concentrate on the study-level documentation (<https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/document/study-level.aspx>).

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Describe all the types of documentation (README files, metadata, etc.) you will provide to help secondary users to find, understand and reuse your data.
- ❖ Following the FAIR (<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>) principles will help you ensure the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Re-usability of your data.
- ❖ Know the minimum requirements for data documentation; see, for example, Qvain Light (<https://www.fairdata.fi/en/qvain/qvain-light-user-guide/>).
- ❖ Use research instruments, which create standardised metadata formats automatically.
- ❖ Identify the types of information that should be captured to enable other researchers to discover, access, interpret, use and cite your data.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly outlines the documentation needed to enable data re-use.
- ❖ Lists the metadata standards used for each data type OR describes how the documentation protocol is agreed (and documented), If no metadata standard is available for a data type.
- ❖ Refers to documentation requirements of a data repositories/archives planned to use.
- ❖ Outlines who is/are responsible for the documentation during the data lifecycle (collection, analysis, storing, publishing, etc.)

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Clearly outlines the documentation needed to enable data re-use.
- ❖ Indicates how the data will be organised during the project (for example naming conventions, version control strategy and folder structures).
- ❖ Mentions common data documentation elements like, a 'readme' text file, file headers, code books, lab notebooks.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides little or no details on the metadata that will accompany the data.
- ❖ Provides no information, or only a very vague mention of documentation, without providing any detail or explanation.

4. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROJECT

4.1 Storage & Security

Describe where you will store and back up your data during your research project. Explain the methods for preserving and sharing your data after your research project has ended in more detail in Section 5.

Consider who will be responsible for backup and recovery. If there are several researchers involved, create a plan with your collaborators and ensure safe transfer between participants.

Show that you are aware of the storing solutions provided by your organisation. Do not merely refer to IT services. In the end, you are responsible for your data, not the IT department or the organisation.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ The use of a safe and secure storage provided and maintained by your organisation's IT support or other reliable IT provider such as CSC is preferable.
- ❖ Do NOT USE external hard drives as the main storing option.
- ❖ Follow your institution's data security requirements

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

Clearly describes:

- ❖ why a certain storage solution has been chosen during the active research phase. Explains the reason if the chosen solution is NOT home institution's or CSC's storage solution,
- ❖ home institution's, CSC's or other service provider's suitable data storing places,
- ❖ the backup policy IF home institution's or CSC's storage solution is NOT used,
- ❖ the version management system for each data type in terms of data security and privacy, performance, capacity, usability and sustainability.
- ❖ storing physical data

SATISFACTORY:

Describes:

- ❖ the location where the data will be stored during the research activities recognizing the possible limitations caused by types of data.
- ❖ the backup policy IF home institution's or CSC's storing services are NOT used (e.g. backup schedule and method)

Even a link to a service description can be sufficient.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides no information or very vague reference to how data will be stored and backed up during the project.
- ❖ Does not show adequate understanding on the systems suitable for storing different types of data.

4.2 Related (Data Security) Policies

It is essential to consider data security issues, especially if your data include sensitive data, personal data, politically sensitive information or trade secrets. Describe who has access to your data, what they are authorised to do with the data, or how you will ensure the safe transfer of data to your collaborators.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Access controls should always be in line with the level of confidentiality involved.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

Clearly describes:

- ❖ who will be responsible for controlling access to the data platform(s),
- ❖ how the access will be controlled,
- ❖ what kinds of appropriate safeguards, e.g. log file system is used, if any.
- ❖ who has access to project data and what they are authorised to do with the data,
- ❖ how the safe data transfer to collaborators will be secured.
- ❖ the access control of physical locations, if data is stored in researcher's own premises.

SATISFACTORY:

Describes

- ❖ who will be responsible for controlling access to the data platform(s),
- ❖ how the access will be controlled.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides little or no details on who will control the access to the data platform(s) during the research, and how.
- ❖ Provides little or no details about data protection and risk management, or the explanation is too vague, (especially when sensitive data are involved).

5. OPENING, PUBLISHING AND ARCHIVING THE DATA AFTER THE RESEARCH PROJECT

5.1 Data Sharing

Describe how you will make data available and findable for reuse. If your data or parts of the data cannot be opened, explain why you publish only metadata.

In the case of sensitive data, which cannot be opened, describe the opening of its metadata. Describe the secured preservation procedure of sensitive data in Section 5.2.

The openness of research data promotes its reuse.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ You can publish a description (i.e., the metadata) of your data without making the data itself openly available, which enables you to restrict access to the data.
- ❖ Publish your data in a data repository or a data journal.
- ❖ Check [re3data.org](https://www.re3data.org/) (<https://www.re3data.org/>) to find a repository for your data.
- ❖ Prefer repositories or publishers, which provide persistent identifiers (PID) to enable access and citation to the data via a persistent link (e.g. DOI, URN).
- ❖ Remember to check the funder, institutional, disciplinary or national recommendations for data repositories.
- ❖ It is recommended to make all of the research data, code and software created within a research project available for reuse, for example, under a Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/choose/>), GNU (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>) or MIT license (<https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>), or under another relevant license.

AVOID OVERLAPS WITH THE PUBLICATION PLAN! The research article publication does not equal data publication. The data journal is a publication forum specialised in publishing research data.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly describes how and when the data and/or metadata, or software will be made discoverable and shared, under which license.
- ❖ Includes the name and the rationale behind chosen repository, data catalogue, or registry where data will or could be shared with PIDs.
- ❖ Clearly explains, if applicable, why data sharing is limited or not possible, and who can access the data under which conditions (for example, only members of certain communities or via a sharing agreement).
- ❖ Clearly indicates which specific tools or software (for example specific scripts, codes, or algorithms developed during the project, version of the software) potential users may need to access, interpret, and (re-)use the data.
- ❖ Provides information, if relevant, on any protocol to access the data (for example if authentication is needed or if there is a data access request procedure).
- ❖ Anticipates how the data can be re-used in other contexts.
- ❖ Ensures that the data, metadata and software are shared under licenses which provide maximum reusability and openness.

SATISFACTORY:

Describes

- ❖ which data and/or metadata or software will be shared,
- ❖ the preliminary schedule and place for sharing,
- ❖ which data and/or metadata or software will not be shared, with the reason for not sharing.

POOR:

- ❖ Provides little or no details on how and when data and/or metadata or software will be shared, or the explanation is not adequate or technically viable.
- ❖ Misunderstands the difference between open access publishing of research articles and sharing of the data.

5.2 Preservation

Briefly describe what part of your data you will preserve, where it is preserved, and for how long. Long term preservation means that data is preserved for as long as necessary, for several decades or even centuries.

You can categorise your data sets according to the anticipated preservation period:

- A) Data to be destroyed upon the ending of the project
- B) Data to be archived for a verification period, which varies across disciplines, e.g., 5–15 years
- C) Data to be archived for potential re-use, e.g., for 25 years
- D) Data with long-term value to be archived by a curated facility for future generations for tens or hundreds of years

You will need to decide which of your research data to preserve and dispose of. Data that is unique or difficult to replicate might have long-term value and be fit for preservation. Special long term data repositories should be used for digital preservation.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Decisions about preserving data should begin during the data management planning stage, and should take into account eg. institutional guidance and requirements.
- ❖ Use data repositories with a commitment to long-term curation, e.g. Digital Preservation Service for Research Data (<https://www.fairdata.fi/en/fairdata-pas/>) is dedicated for research datasets that have significant value to the organization or on a national level currently and especially also in the future. Contact your home organisation for further information.
- ❖ Additionally, describe if some part of the data is disposed of after the project and how is the data destroyed.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Specifies and categorizes datasets that need different length of preservation:
 - ❖ A) data to be destroyed after the project. Describes how the data will be disposed after preservation period.
 - ❖ B) data to be archived for a verification period, e.g. 5-15 years.
 - ❖ C) data to be archived or potential re-use, e.g. for 25 years;
 - ❖ D) data to be preserved and curated for tens or hundreds of years.
- ❖ Describes how reliable management, archiving and admission to the datasets will be secured when needed because of verification, agreements or other reasons.
- ❖ Acknowledges the impact of legal, ownership, agreements, and funders', institution's, and publishers' demands on data preservation.
- ❖ Provides the name of the archive or trustworthy repository - or the way to curate and preserve data - that will be used to make data available for re-use.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Describes what part of the data will be archived, where and for how long.
- ❖ Acknowledges the difference between storing of data vs. long-term preservation (archiving) of data.
- ❖ Acknowledges impact of legal, ownership, agreements, funders', publishers' and institutions' demands on data preservation

POOR:

- ❖ Does not acknowledge the difference between storing of data vs. long-term preservation (archiving) of data.
- Provides no further information or lacks adequate explanation what is planned about preservation.
- Does not take into account legal or other aspects which can make long-term preservation of the data impossible.

6. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Roles & Responsibilities

Summarise here all the roles and responsibilities described in the previous answers. Also, consider who will be responsible for the data resulting from your project after your project has ended.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities, for example, data capture, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving, and data sharing. Name the responsible individual(s) where possible.
- ❖ For collaborative projects, explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners.
- ❖ Indicate who is responsible for implementing the DMP and for ensuring that it is reviewed and, if necessary, revised.
- ❖ Consider scheduling regular updates of the DMP.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Clearly outlines all the roles and responsibilities described in the DMP and names the individuals where possible: e.g. data management / stewardship, data capture, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving, and data sharing.
- ❖ Clearly states who is responsible for the data resulting from the project after the project has ended.
- ❖ Clearly states the procedure for transferring these responsibilities (in case the person is expected to leave the project).
- ❖ Explains how data management responsibilities are co-ordinated in collaborative projects.
- ❖ Indicates who is responsible for implementing the DMP and updating it during the project.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Describes data management roles and responsibilities and/or mentions that responsibility will be taken for data management without giving details of who / which processes. Does not clearly state who is responsible of the data resulting from the project after it has ended.
- ❖ Provides some information but does not give a clear statement how data management is taken care of in collaborative projects.
- ❖ It is mentioned that the DMP will be updated, but implementation and responsibilities are not specified.

POOR:

- ❖ Does not discuss responsibility for data management/ stewardship activities and/ or does not indicate who is responsible for day-to-day implementation and adjustments to the DMP.
- ❖ Provides no description, in case of a collaborative project, on how data management responsibilities will be co-ordinated across partners.

6.2 Budget

Estimate the resources, such as time and financial costs, needed to manage, share and preserve the data. These may include storage costs, hardware, staff time, the costs of preparing data for deposit and repository charges.

TIPS FOR BEST PRACTICES

- ❖ Consider, if there will be additional costs from computational facilities or resources that need to be accessed.
- ❖ Account for resources, time and money, needed to prepare the data for sharing it and preservation (data curation).
- ❖ Remember to specify your data management costs in the budget, according to funder requirements.

DMP PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

EXCELLENT:

- ❖ Lists the required resources and facilities for data management (e.g. storing environment, computational facilities, hardware, staff time for preparing data for sharing, deposit, and repository charges) and refers to the specified financial costs in the budget, according to funder requirements.
- ❖ Provides estimates of time and money needed to prepare the data for sharing, publishing, preservation (data curation).
- ❖ Describes investments to expertise, like how lawyer, data steward, IT expert's consultancy is purchased, or are these experts hired to the project.
- ❖ Outlines what kind of resources is needed on training and education to upscale data management skills needed.

SATISFACTORY:

- ❖ Refers to the project budget and mentions some of the required resources (e.g. storing environment, computational facilities, hardware), but does not list the resources or specify the expected financial costs.
- ❖ Mentions but does not give an estimate of the time and money needed to prepare the data for sharing and preservation (data curation).

POOR:

- ❖ Provides no answer or is vague about the resources required for data management (e.g. resources are not listed and time for data management is not allocated).
- ❖ Does not refer to the project budget regarding data management resources and costs.